

BIOECOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF TOXIC ELEMENT CONCENTRATES INCURRED FROM FISH MEAT CONSUMPTION USING BIOACCUMULATION FACTOR OF SELECTED AQUATIC BIOSPHERE

***¹Okolotu G.I., ²Nwadiolu R., ³Akwenuke O.M. and ⁴Eze P.C.**

¹Department of Agricultural Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Southern Delta University, P.M.B. 05, Ozoro, Nigeria.

²Department of Agricultural Extension, Faculty of Agriculture, Southern Delta University, P.M.B. 05, Ozoro, Nigeria.

³Department of Civil and Water Resources Engineering, Southern Delta University, P.M.B. 05, Ozoro, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Agricultural and Bioresource Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, P.M.B.01, Enugu, Nigeria.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18610055>

Keywords:

Aquatic Meat Consumption; Bioecology; Bioaccumulation Factor; Aquatic Biosphere; Tilapia; Catfish; etc.

Abstract: *The need for more understanding of water habitations prompted the relevance of this study main objective "bioecological assessment of toxic element concentrates incurred from fish meat consumption using bioaccumulation factor of selected aquatic biosphere". Fish species of Tilapia and Catfish (24 pieces each) harnessed from their colonies, and ten gallons of water from their habitat were deployed for analysis. Adsorption techniques were used in obtaining toxic elements test values applied in deducing necessary bioaccumulation factor, pinpointing the bioecological status. Conclusively, the bioecology of the selected aquatic biosphere possessed low toxic elements concentrations, with low bioaccumulation factor, (BAF) ranging between 0 - 5.125. Good pre and post harvest hygienic handling and proper processing methods likes cooking, frying, drying, smoking, etc., were profered as additives in minimizing the rate of these toxics Incurred by humans from aquatic meats.*

***Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.**

I. INTRODUCTION

The toxic status of an ecology with specification of biological organisms in aquatic biospheres are of great deal to our understanding, for instance the rate of poisonous elements accumulation tends to affect aquatic biological spheres which impacts on humans through food chain interaction prior contact upon consumption. Moreso, the rate and nature of the bioecological impact influences the strategic input by man towards management and conservation of the biosphere. This calls for the attention of water professionals, environmental experts, agricultural personnels, biological and ecological workers, chemical and toxic specialists, nature policy makers, *etc.*

Aquatic Meat Consumption is of continual increase locally and globally. Nigeria is blessed with numerous human and natural resources, having 14 million hectares of reservoirs, lakes, ponds and major rivers (Ngodigha *et al.*, 2018). Most of these water resources are deployed for aquatic meat harnessment, according to fishing policies, towards meeting economic and consumption demand. The operating range of small – scale fisheries at apparently 20m depth

contour, extending occasionally to a maximum depth of 40m and 5 neautical miles away from shores (Ngodigha *et al.*, 2018), paving way for large production, even at local levels. The above stated production resources and strategy are expected to contributively provide for both domestic and foreign consumption demand. In 2020, Asian countries were the main producers, accounting for 70 percent of the total fisheries and aquacultural production of aquatic animals, followed by countries in the Americas (12 percent), Europe (10 percent), Africa (7 percent) and Oceania (1 percent) (FAO, 2022). This portray Nigeria and Africa as potential consumers relying on importation. FAO, (2022), added that China continued to be the major producer with a share of 35 percent of the total, followed by India (8 percent), Indonesia (7 percent), Vietnam (5 percent) and Peru (3 percent). The global trend in aquatic consumption is presented in figure one (1) below, where it can be seen that, Nigeria is not among the top nor least but average consumer globally, though its continent, Africa seems the least consumer worldwide.

Figure 1: Aquatic food consumption 2017 - 2019 (FAO, 2020)

Moreso, production of healthy and toxic free aquatic meat is vital to justify meeting consumption goals. Anater *et al.*, (2016), registered some emerging primary consequent concerns on market available fish quality, pointing that the presence of chemical residues in any product of aquatic animal origin could be of health risk to animals and human.

Bioecology is the biological aspects of the study of the relationships of living organisms with their environment, as well as with each other. LAR, (2022), defined bioecology as the study of the relationships between the living things and their environment. Bioecology is gaining widespread from its current momentum. It is vastly conceived and interpreted as the combination of biology and ecology. The term biology from greek words 'bios' meaning 'life', and 'logos' meaning 'study', definable as the scientific study of life as well as living organisms (NTNU, 2025). Also, BES, (2024), explained the term ecology (coined by Ernst Haeckel in 1866), from the greek words

'oikos,' meaning house (our planet earth), and 'logy' meaning knowledge. Both knowledges contribute to more understanding of the environment aiding conservatory measures. Murray-Bligh and Griffiths, (2022), emphasized that a good water management is attributive to a crucial element of biological and ecological assessment. BES, (2024), identified water, every element, fire, pressure, gravity, temperature, volcanoes, wind, deserts, woodlands, oceans, storms, cities, beaches, and every system as components that make up the environment.

Bioaccumulation Factor Is the factor upon which substance accumulation processes in the tissues of living organisms are studied in relation to an environment. Słoczyńska *et al.*, (2023), defined bioaccumulation as "the uptake of substances from the environment, an accumulation over time, or retention of a substance". According to Arnot and Gobas, (2006), "Bioaccumulation assessment is important in the scientific evaluation of risks that chemicals may pose to humans and the environment and is a current focus of regulatory effort". It is mostly used for toxics that form in a

*Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.

food chain. BAF can be assessed by field or laboratory experiments. Arnot and Gobas, (2006), pointed on the importance of environmental measurement for reliable assessment with emphasis on field BAFs tending to be greater than the laboratory BCFs. Biochemical factors including the bioaccumulation factor (BAF), bioconcentration factor (BCF), biomagnification factor (BMF), trophic magnification factor (TMF), and biota-sediment accumulation factor (BSAF), exist over the years (Ochoa-Esteso *et al.*, 2024). Armitage *et al.*, (2021), categorically differentiated field based like the bioaccumulation factor (BAF), and trophic magnification factor (TMF), from the laboratory based like the bioconcentration factor (BCF) and biomagnification factor (BMF) using B-metrics, while associating “not bioaccumulative” (nB), “bioaccumulative” (B), or “very bioaccumulative” (vB) to assessment categorization.

Aquatic Biosphere refers to the water environment of any biomes (regional biological

community). It covers about seventy - five percent (75 %) of the earth surface, marking the largest of all biomes (NGS, 2023). NWU, (2017), identified aquatic systems relative to biosphere in planet earth to include the oceans, rivers, lakes, ponds, estuaries, coastal lagoons, mangrove swamps, coral reefs, wetlands, cenotes, reservoirs, underground deposits, and, fjords. Aquatic biosphere is categorized into freshwater and saltwater. Generally, a biosphere is a sectional part of the planet earth, with life support capability. It is a sphere connecting biological organisms to various sphere like the atmosphere (relating to air which provide additional oxygen, natural enrichment, *etc*), hydrosphere (relating to water which provide maneuverability, natural stabilization, *etc*), and lithosphere (relating to land which provide underwater bed as base for rest, protection, *etc*). It can be seen in figure two (2) below;

***Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.**

Figure 2: Sphere types and biosphere (NWU, 2017)

II. MATERIALS

The Study Area is the fishing axis at the cliffs of Otu Ogwu, in Asaba Delta - Anambra Niger river, which provided the ground base for this work. Asaba lies approximately 60 degrees north of the equator and distanced at about 160 kilometres to where the River Niger flows into the Atlantic Ocean (Okolotu, and Oluka, 2021), at the gulf of Nigeria. Asaba, the capital of delta state of Nigeria, is sited on the Niger river right bank (DSG, 2024). Asaba is a connector to the eastern, western, northern, and southern parts of Nigeria through water (Niger river) and through land (Head bridges - roads). Within this study area, the aquatic environment toxic data, as well as the analyzed fish species were obtained.

Tilapia is a native fish in Africa and Middle east. It belongs to the genus *Tilapia*. According to Sorensen, and Levesque, (2024), tilapia is a common name to a few dozen cichlid fish from Africa in the order Cichliformes, family Cichlidae which diverged about 250 million years ago. Tilapia cultivation in the recent past, have shown significant acceleration, due to its palatability, fast growth, and high protein content (Aich *et al.*, 2022). At the global scale, the tilapia is among the most extensively cultivated fish (Cano-Lozano *et al.*, 2022).

Catfish is a fish most found in freshwater bodies. It has no scales and possesses barbels like the projected long hairs that grows at the

mouth sides of cats. Over the past several years, catfishes have continually surged to vie with the tilapia fishes for the global position of the number two most cultivated fish group worldwide (Lutz, 2024). In Nigeria, it is popularized as point and kill fish. The ideology of naming it "point and kill" is associated to its fastly readily usage as pepper soup or fish sauce, upon choosing by pointing, at various social arenas or eateries. With over 3000 recognized catfish species, it is marketed in Africa upon harvest, as live products, smoked or even dried (Lutz, 2024), and fried. In the terrestrial environments, catfish is an ideal model for establishing adaptation understanding due to its survival immunity (Lisachov *et al.*, 2023).

III. METHODOLOGY

Tilapia and catfish (24 pieces each) were deployed for this assessment upon harnessing, and laboratory sampling and analysis for toxic element presence using adsorption technique. Same were ten galons of water samply obtained and tested for toxic element presence with respect to level of concentration using adsorption technique. Their bioaccumulation factor were calculated on the basis of the ratio of toxic element concentration level in animal body to that of the ambient aquatic media. This was in accordance to Agarwal *et. al.*, (2022) formula presented in equation one (1) below;

$$\text{BAF} = \frac{\text{Con}_{\text{tissue}}}{\text{Con}_{\text{water}}} \quad (\text{eq. I})$$

*Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.

where, C_{tissue} is the concentration of toxic elements in tissue or internal system. C_{water} is the concentration of toxic elements in water. Also, from results obtained from the selected aquatic biosphere, toxicity was further

compared using WHO, (2003), standard for consumption.

IV. RESULTS

The results obtained are presented in tables one (1) to three (3), and figures three (3) to five (5) below;

Table 1: Tilapia data for toxicity (environment and meat content) and bioaccumulation

S/N	Toxic Element Type	Aquatic Environment Toxic Content (mg/kg)	Fish Meat Toxic Content (mg/kg)	Bioaccumulation Content
1	Cadmium, Cd	0.082	0.004	0.0488
2	Chromium, Cr	0.63	0.08	0.1270
3	Copper, Cu	0.9	1.2	1.3333
4	Iron, Fe	0.07	0.2	2.8571
5	Lead, Pb	0.02	0.008	0.4
6	Manganese, Mn	0.08	0.12	1.5
7	Mercury, Hg	0.007	0.003	0.4286
8	Zinc, Zn	0.09	0.12	1.3333
Total	-	1.8790	1.7350	8.0281
Average	-	0.2349	0.2169	1.0035

Table 2: Catfish data for toxicity (environment and meat content) and bioaccumulation

S/N	Toxic Element Type	Aquatic Environment Toxic Content (mg/kg)	Fish Meat Toxic Content (mg/kg)	Bioaccumulation Content
1	Cadmium, Cd	0.082	0.060	0.7317

***Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.**

2	Chromium, Cr	0.63	0.01	0.0159
3	Copper, Cu	0.9	1.1	1.2222
4	Iron, Fe	0.07	0.3	4.2857
5	Lead, Pb	0.02	0.013	0.65
6	Manganese, Mn	0.08	0.41	5.125
7	Mercury, Hg	0.007	0.002	0.2857
8	Zinc, Zn	0.09	0.16	1.7778
Total	-	1.8790	2.001	14.0940
Average	-	0.2349	0.2501	1.7618

Table 3: Bioaccumulation variation

S/N	Toxic Element Type	Tilapia Bioaccumulation Content	Catfish Bioaccumulation Content	Fish Species BAF Deviation
1	Cadmium, Cd	0.0488	0.7317	0.6829
2	Chromium, Cr	0.1270	0.0159	0.1111
3	Copper, Cu	1.3333	1.2222	0.1111
4	Iron, Fe	2.8571	4.2857	1.4286
5	Lead, Pb	0.4	0.65	0.25
6	Manganese, Mn	1.5	5.125	3.625
7	Mercury, Hg	0.4286	0.2857	0.1429
8	Zinc, Zn	1.3333	1.7778	0.4445
Total	-	8.0281	14.0940	6.7961
Average	-	1.0035	1.7618	0.8495

The levels of toxics for the aquatic environment, fish meat and bioaccumulation for tilapia specie are presented in figure three (3) below;

Figure 3: Levels of toxics for the aquatic environment, fish meat and bioaccumulation for tilapia specie

The levels of toxics for the aquatic environment, fish meat and bioaccumulation for catfish specie are presented in figure four (4) below;

***Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.**

Figure 4: Levels of toxics for the aquatic environment, fish meat and bioaccumulation for catfish specie

The bioaccumulation variations from tilapia and catfish species of the selected aquatic biosphere are presented in figure five (5) below;

Figure 5: Fish species bioaccumulation (BAF) variations in the aquatic biosphere

V. DISCUSSION

From results obtained in this work, the conditions of the toxic elements in the aquatic environment or selected aquatic biosphere showed that: Cd was below, Cr was above, Cu was below, Fe was below, Pb was above, Mn was higher, Zn was above, compared with the international standard provided by WHO, (2003) recommendation of 0.003 Cd, 0.05 Cr, 2.0 Cu, < 0.1 Fe, 0.01 Pb, < 0.05 Mn, 0.1 Zn, as the safety limits for toxics in liquid consumption which invariably suggests that above these

levels, consumers are likely taking in poisons which may be harmful to health at any point.

Also, it was observed that at some instances, the fishes dwelled in water environment with higher chemical contents without the fish internal system incurring equivalent or more fraction of the chemicals even though they consume same water containing these said toxic elements. This observatory finding relates to the case of sea fishes habitated in salt waters and yet requiring salt spice addition to meet human salt tastes, pointing that they seem to possess mechanisms of controlling substantial contents of such substances. Though, other factors may contribute to such outcome. Such ideology tally with the work of Lisachov *et al.*, (2023), that established the understanding in their review

***Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.**

work, stating that, catfish possess auxiliary breathing organs for survival in challenging aquatic environments of high salt concentrations, some high toxics, and low oxygen, through the help of their specialized physiological mechanisms.

VI. CONCLUSION

From results obtained, it was concluded that the bioecology of the selected aquatic biosphere studied possessed low toxic elements concentration, with low bioaccumulation factors (BAF), with the BAF ranging from 0 - 5.125. At the above range, consumption of these animals are of less threat to human. The fish species

REFERENCES

NTNU, 2025. What Is Biology?. NTNU – Norwegian University Of Science And Technology, Norway. P 1. <https://ntnu.edu/biology/about-us/what-is-biology>

BES, 2024. The Official Definition Of Ecology: “The Study Of Relationships Between Living Things And Their Environment”. British Ecological Society, London, UK. P 2 & 3. <https://www.britishecologicalsociety.org/what-is-ecology/#:~:text=The%20official%20definition%20of%20ecology,Our%20house%20is%20planet%20Earth.>

BAF variations were less than 4. This is to say that neither of the species possess significantly variant or intensifiably difference in relation to the rate of these toxic elements accumulation as obtained from the aquatic biosphere. The above conclusively obtained facts summarily points that these fish meats of the said biosphere are encouragingly of a consumptive greenlight. However, proper finishing processing techniques not excluding cooking, frying, drying, smoking, *etc.*, are welcoming, as well as good pre and post harvest sanitary handling to minimize rate of these toxics Incurred by humans from aquatic meats.

DSG, 2024. About Delta. Delta State Government. Delta State To The World. P 5. <https://deltastate.gov.ng/about-delta/>

Lutz C.G., 2024. Catfishes. Encyclopedia Of Meat Sciences (Third Edition). Science Direct. Volume 2024. P 58 & 61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-85125-1.00117-4>

Ochoa-Esteso C., Roselló-Carrió A., Carrasco-Correa E.J., & Lerma-García M.J., 2024. Bioaccumulation Of Environmental Pollutants And Marine Toxins In Bivalve Molluscs: A Review. Exploration Of Foods And Foodomics. Volume 2024. Special Issue 2. P 801. <https://doi.org/10.37349/eff.2024.00062>

***Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.**

Sorensen P.W., & Levesque H.L., 2024. Hormonal Pheromones: Actions Of Hormones And Their Metabolites Outside The Body. Encyclopedia Of Fish Physiology (Second Edition). Volume 2024. P 317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-90801-6.00111-7>

Lisachov A., Nguyen D.H.M., Panthum T., Ahmad S.F., Singchat W., Ponjarat J., Jaisamut K., Srisapoom P., Duengkae P., Hatachote S., Sriphairoj K., Muangmai N., Unajak S., Han K., N-Nakorn U., & Srikulnath K., 2023. Emerging Importance Of Bighead Catfish (Clarias Macrocephalus) And North African Catfish (C. Gariepinus) As A Bioresource And Their Genomic Perspective - Review. Aquaculture. Volume 573. Number 739585. P 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2023.739585>

NGS, 2023. Aquatic Biome. Geographic Education Centre - National Geographic Society, Washington, United States Of America. P 1. <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/aquatic-biome/>

Słoczyńska K., Orzeł J., Murzyn A., Popiół J., Gunia-Krzyżak A., Koczurkiewicz-Adamczyk P., & Pękala E., 2023. Antidepressant Pharmaceuticals In

Aquatic Systems, Individual - Level Ecotoxicological Effects: Growth, Survival And Behavior. Aquatic Toxicology. Volume 260. Number 106554. P 9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquatox.2023.106554>

Agarwal S., Albeshr M.F., Mahboob S., Atique U., Pramanick P., & Mitra A., 2022. Bioaccumulation Factor (BAF) Of Heavy Metals In Green Seaweed To Assess The Phytoremediation Potential. Journal Of King Saud University - Science. Volume 34, Issue 5. P 6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksus.2022.102078>

Aich N., Paul A., Choudhury T.G., & Saha H., 2022. Tilapia Lake Virus (TiLV) Disease: Current Status Of Understanding. Aquaculture And Fisheries. Volume 7. Issue 1. P 8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aaf.2021.04.007>

Cano-Lozano J.A., Diaz L.M.V., Bolivar J.F.M., Hume M.E., & Pardo R.Y.R., 2022. Probiotics In Tilapia (Oreochromis Niloticus) Culture: Potential Probiotic Lactococcus Lactis Culture Conditions - Review. Journal Of Bioscience And Bioengineering. Volume 133. Issue 3. P 187. P 1.

***Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.**

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiosc.2021.11.004>

FAO, 2022. The State Of World Fisheries And Aquaculture Towards Blue Transformation. Food And Agriculture Organization Of The United Nations, Rome. P 8.
<https://doi.org/10.4060/cc0461en>

LAR, 2022. Bioecology The Science Of Connection. Long Acres Range. P 1.
[https://longacresranch.org/bioecology-the-science-of-connection/#:~:text=In%20short%2C%20bioecology%20\(or%20ecology,living%20things%20and%20their%20environment](https://longacresranch.org/bioecology-the-science-of-connection/#:~:text=In%20short%2C%20bioecology%20(or%20ecology,living%20things%20and%20their%20environment)

Murray-Bligh J., & Griffiths M., 2022. Practitioners Guide To Improving And Protecting River Health. Freshwater Biology And Ecology Handbook - The Foundation For Water Research. P 1.
<https://fwr.org/publication/freshwater-biology-and-ecology-handbook/>

Armitage J.M., Toose L., Camenzuli L., Redman A.D., Parkerton T.F., Saunders D., Wheeler J., Martin A., Vaiopoulou E., & Arnot J.A., 2021. A Critical Review And Weight Of Evidence Approach For Assessing The Bioaccumulation Of Phenanthrene In Aquatic Environments. Willey - Integrated Environmental

Assessment And Management. Volume 17, Issue 5. P 911.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4401>

Okolotu G.I., & Oluka, S.I., 2021. Shore Reclamation For Agricultural Use, A Combat To Shoreline Erosion. Advance Journal Of Science, Engineering And Technology Volume: 6; Issue: 5. P 17.
<https://aspjournals.org/ajset/index.php/ajset/article/view/28>

Ngodigha S.A., Alogoa J.K., & Abowei J.F., 2018. Status And Constrains Of Artisanal Fisheries In Ekperikiri Fishing Area, Niger Delta. Anals Of Ecology And Environmental Science, Vol 2, Issue 4. P 24 & 25. <https://doi.org/10.22259/2637-5338.0204004>

NWU, 2017. Water On Planet Earth: Aquatic Biogeochemistry. North Western University. P 1 & 2.
<https://sites.northwestern.edu/monroyrios/2017/12/26/water-planet-earth/>

Anater A., Manyes L., Meca G., Ferrer E., Luciano F.B., Pimpão C.T., & Font G., 2016. Mycotoxins And Their Consequences In Aquaculture: A review. Aquaculture. Volume 451. P 3.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2015.08.022>

***Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.**

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 9; Issue: 01,

January-February, 2026

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 9.15

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ijess>

Arnot J.A., & Gobas F.A., 2006. A Review Of Bioconcentration Factor (BCF) And Bioaccumulation Factor (BAF) Assessments For Organic Chemicals In Aquatic Organisms. Environmental Reviews. P 1. <https://doi.org/10.1139/a06-005>

WHO, 2003. Zinc In Drinking - Water. World Health Organization (WHO/SDE/WSH/03.04/17). P 3. https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/wash-documents/wash-chemicals/zinc.pdf?sfvrsn=9529d066_4

***Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M. and Eze P.C.**